

A Comparative Study on Deployment of Open Source Learning Management System Moodle on Different Cloud Vendors

Dr. Rubin Thottupurathu Jose
Associate Professor
Amal Jyothi College of
Engineering
Kottayam, India
rubinthottupuram@amaljyothi.ac.in

Ms. Sona Maria Sebastian
Assistant Professor
Amal Jyothi College of
Engineering
Kottayam, India
sonasebastian@amaljyothi.ac.in

Ms. Shelly Shiju George
Assistant Professor
Amal Jyothi College of
Engineering
Kottayam, India
shellyshijugeorge@amaljyothi.ac.in

Ms. Jetty Benjamin
Assistant Professor
Amal Jyothi College of
Engineering
Kottayam, India
jettybenjamin@amaljyothi.ac.in

Mr. Jinson Devis
Assistant Professor
Amal Jyothi College of
Engineering
Kottayam, India
jinsondevis@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract-Cloud is collection of huge resources like computing power in terms of virtual machines, server storage, RAM memory which will be available to the users on-demand. Cloud provides many services in comparatively very low price. The users can setup their own datacenters on-premises that can cost huge amount for purchasing as well as for maintenance.

Cloud computing refers to services and applications which run in a distributed network using virtualized resources. A revolutionary new approach was adopted in cloud computing where the infrastructure, storage, computers and network capacity are leased or rented. Resources are limitless, scalable with agility and universally available. Computing has become reliable and faster and as a result dependency on the services offered by cloud has increased drastically. There are many cloud service providers which offers cloud services to customers. Choosing the vendors which offers maximum features at reasonable and affordable price is needed. In this paper we are comparing the features offered by Moodle Cloud and GCP Moodle Cloud on various parameters.

Keywords - Cloud computing, Moodle Cloud, GCP Moodle Cloud

I. INTRODUCTION

Moodle LMS is a free and open-source learning management system. User-friendly Interface, Security, Easy Backup, Convenient file management, Customizable site design and layout are the key features of Moodle. During this pandemic situation Moodle is useful for distance education, flipped classroom etc. in schools, universities and other sectors. With its functionality and plugin capabilities, Moodle offers an engaging and effective eLearning experience for students of all ages.

GCP Moodle have been deployed as a docker image and that the docker image have dependency libraries and the operating system incorporated. Bitnami has partnered with Google to make Moodle LMS available in the Google Cloud Platform. A Docker image includes the elements needed to run an application as a container -- such as code, config files, environment variables, libraries and run time.

II. COMPARISON PARAMETERS

a. Comparison of Features

Since Moodle is an open source LMS, anyone can configure Moodle by their own. moodlecloud.com is such a third-party vendor

which provide users to have their own Moodle site up and running in a short time frame.

GCP Moodle is deployed in Google Cloud Platform and is used to manage academic

activities in Amal Jyothi College of Engineering.

b. Based on detailed comparison of the key Features of Moodle Cloud and GCP Moodle, the following conclusions have come up.

Table 1. Comparison of Features

Comparison of Features			
Sl. No.	Key Features	Moodle Cloud	GCP Moodle
1	Maximum Users	500	3200 +
2	Computing Power	2 vCPU (1 VM)	11 vCPU (6 VMs)
3	Memory	6 GB	32 GB
4	Storage	2.5 GB	700 GB
5	Latest Moodle version	Yes	Yes
6	Unlimited courses & activities	Yes	Yes
7	Personalised site name	Yes	Yes
8	Mobile app enabled	Yes	Yes
9	Web conferencing with BBB	Yes	Yes
10	Max concurrent video conferencing users	100	3200+
11	Session recording	Yes	Yes
12	Custom certificates	Yes	Yes
13	Document converter	Yes	Yes
14	Automated backups	Yes	Yes
15	Plugin and theme installation	No	Yes
16	Scalability	No	Yes
17	Deployment Mode	No Information	Container-based Deployment
18		No Information Regarding Customization for Clearance of Log Files	Can Customize Clearance of Log Files

c. Comparison of Price Based on Computing Power

In computing, computer performance is the amount of useful work accomplished by a computer system. Outside of specific contexts,

computer performance is estimated in terms of accuracy, efficiency and speed of executing computer program instructions.

Computing power is an important aspect in Moodle. Increase in computing speed increases

the overall performance of Moodle. i.e., Higher the computing speed, higher the overall system

performance. High Computing power with affordable cost is now important.

Table 2. Comparison of Price Based on Computing Power

Comparison of Price Based on Computing Power				
Sl. No.	Moodle Cloud	Cost (INR)/Year	GCP Moodle	Cost (INR)/Year
1	2 vCPU (1 VM)	63878.75	2 vCPU (1 VM)	50674.08
2	4 vCPU (2 VM)	113562.21	4 vCPU (2 VM)	1,01,348.16
3	6 vCPU (3 VM)	1,91,636.25	6 vCPU (3 VM)	1,52,022.24
4	8 vCPU (4 VM)	2,55,515	8 vCPU (4 VM)	2,02,696.32
5	10 vCPU (5 VM)	3,19,393.75	10 vCPU (5 VM)	2,53,370.4
6	12 vCPU (6 VM)	3,83,272.5	12 vCPU (6 VM)	3,04,044.48

d. Comparison of Memory Based on Number of VMs

According to the comparison of features of the basic given data, Moodle Cloud provides 6GB of memory for 1VM whereas GCP Moodle provides 32GB for 6VMs. When we are comparing memory based on number of VMs, Moodle Cloud is working with **6GB/VM** but

GCP Moodle is working only with 32GB/6VM=**5.33GB/VM**. In practice when we are considering an educational institution with many departments and different types of computational tasks, one VM is not adequate. So, if we consider 6VMs as a standard, Moodle Cloud is considered to support **6GB*6VM=36GB**. GCP Moodle is supporting **32GB** by default.

Table 3. Comparison of Memory Based on Number of VMs

Comparison of Memory Based on Number of VMs			
Sl. No.	Number of VMs	Moodle Cloud	GCP Moodle
1	1 VM	6 GB	32/6 = 5.33 GB (Approx. 6 GB)
2	6 VMs	36 GB (6 *6)	32 GB

e. Comparison of Price Based on Number of Users

Moodle Cloud and GCP Moodle are totally different when we consider the user support and the usage cost per year. From the basic information provided, the price or cost of Moodle Cloud is 63878.75Rs for 310 users. The number of users may be scaled up to a maximum of 500 but the maximum concurrent

video conferencing users are limited to 100 only. Also, the amount should be paid as prior lump-sum. The average monthly post payment for GCP Moodle is 8,454.70Rs and the yearly cost is 1,01,456.4Rs for two VMs. In order to achieve the 3200+ users for an educational institution, three number of 2VM 4vCPU and one 1VM 2vCPU configuration costs 1,13,162.72Rs*3+63645.75Rs=**4,03,133.762R**s in a lump-sum basis in Moodle Cloud. The

GCP Moodle for the same 3200+ users cost
2,87,130Rs only.

Table 4. Comparison of Price Based on Number of Users

Comparison of Price Based on Number of Users					
Sl. No.	Number of Users	Moodle Cloud Price	GCP Moodle Price		
1	500 (2 vCPU , 1 VM)	63878.75 INR (Pre Paid)	8,454.70 (Monthly Payment)	INR Post-	1,01,456.4 INR Yearly (2 VMs)
2	3200+	4,03,133.762 INR (Pre Paid) (1,13,162.72 *3 + 63645.75)	2,87,130 (Monthly Payment)	INR Post-	

Flexible storage capacity at an affordable price is the need of the hour of every business organizations. On demand provisioning, network access and adherence to open standards are the key characteristics of cloud storage. In cloud storage, the storage resources are abstracted from physical hardware through virtualization technology. Cloud storage

pricing depends on various parameters such as data storage, network usage, operations use etc. Storage is calculated in terms of binary gigabytes. We have compared the storage available for Moodle cloud and storage available for GCP Moodle on user basis. File storage in Moodle Cloud means maximum file storage for the entire Moodle Cloud site.

f. Comparison of Storage Based on Number of Users

Table 5. Comparison of Storage Based on Number of Users

Comparison of Storage Based on Number of Users			
Sl. No.	Number of Users	Storage Available - Moodle Cloud	Storage Available - GCP Moodle
1	Single User	5,242.88 B (2.5 GB/500)	2,29,376 B (700 GB /3200)
2	310 maximum of 500	2.5 GB (63878.75 INR (Pre-Paid))	109.375 GB (1,025.464 INR)
3	3200 +	16 GB (4,08,824 INR (Pre-Paid))	700 GB (2,87,130 INR (Monthly Post-Payment))
4		1 GB (25,551.5 INR)	1 GB (410.186 INR)

g. Comparison of Memory Based on Price

Table 6. Comparison of Memory Based on Price

Comparison of Memory Based on Price			
Sl. No.	Memory	Moodle Cloud	GCP Moodle
1	1 GB	10646.46 INR/Year	8972.813 INR/Year
2	6 GB	63878.75 INR/Year	53836.875 INR/Year
3	32 GB	3,40,686.67 INR/Year	2,87,130 INR/Year

h. Comparison of Clouds With All Parameters

Table 7. Comparison of Clouds With All Parameters

Comparison of Clouds With All Parameters					
	Computing Power (2 vCPU & 1VM) in INR	Memory (6 GB) in INR	Storage (2.5 GB) in INR	Users (500) in INR	Price (INR)/Yearly
Moodle Cloud	63878.75	63878.75	63878.75	63878.75	63878.75
GCP Moodle	50674.08	53,836.88	12,305.57	44864.06	50674.08

Figure 1. Comparative Study

i. Comparison of Clouds for Resources Available with Respect to Price (INR 2,88,000)

Table 8. Comparison of Clouds for Resources Available with Respect to Price (INR 2,88,000)

Comparison of Clouds for Resources Available with Respect to Price (INR 2,88,000)					
	Computing (vCPU)	Power	Memory (GB)	Storage (GB)	Users
Moodle Cloud	10		29	12	2400
GCP Moodle	11		32	700	3500

Figure 2. Comparative Study

III. CONCLUSION

The support of memory based on the number of VMs presents an understanding of how the two systems perform well in a real scenario.

Moodle cloud is slightly better with 36GB of memory whereas GCP Moodle supports only 32GB when we consider 6VM as a base.

Another study was about the price comparison based on number of users. We considered 3200+ users as our primary need and found a huge difference in price.

Moodle Cloud costs INR 4,03,133.762 in a lump-sum basis but GCP Moodle cost INR 2,87,130 only.

Based on the comparative study, it can be concluded that the GCP Moodle is more cost effective compared to Moodle Cloud. Not only the prices are comparatively low in GCP Moodle but also it provides more amount of resources to the consumers compared to the Moodle Cloud.